

Niementowski 4-Ketoquinazoline Synthesis. Part I. Modification and Mechanism

V. S. Patel and S. R. Patel

The Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis has been modified to improve its applicability. Evidence for the course of the reaction has been provided and mechanism proposed.

The Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis, consisting in heating an anthranilic acid with formamide, has been widely adapted as a convenient method for the synthesis of Bz-substituted 4-ketoquinazolines¹⁻³. When higher amides are used in place of formamide, higher reaction temperatures are needed and the yields are poor. Mayer and Wagner⁴ tried several modifications for this reaction with a view to improving the yield and applicability. These authors used methyl anthranilate in place of anthranilic acid to prevent decarboxylation of the latter at higher reaction temperatures and used isatoic anhydride and amidine as more reactive substitutes for anthranilic acid and acid amide respectively.

We have found that if *N*-acylanthranilic acid is heated with a slight excess of formamide, the corresponding 2-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline is formed in good yields. Using this modified Niementowski reaction, 2-methyl-, 2-ethyl-, 2-propyl-, 2-phenyl-, 2-benzyl-, 2-*p*-methoxyphenyl-, 2-*p*-nitrophenyl-, 2- β -phenylethyl-, and 2-styryl-4-ketoquinazolines have been synthesised in good yields. 2-Phenyl-4-ketoquinazoline, which could be obtained in extremely poor yield by the Niementowski reaction⁵ between anthranilic acid and benzamide, is formed in about 65% yield on heating *N*-benzoylaminoanthranilic acid with formamide at 165° for 3 hr. For the sake of comparison and mixed melting point, 2-substituted-4-ketoquinazolines, obtained by this modified method, have also been synthesised by alternative methods, described in literature.

The success of this and other similar experiments (*vide infra*) has provided a direct evidence for the course of this reaction which was originally proposed by Bogert and Gotthelf² and convincingly supported by Mayer and Wagner⁴, but mostly by inferential and indirect evidences. According to the proposed course of the reaction, the first stage is the transacylation reaction between anthranilic acid (I) and the acid amide, affording *N*-acylanthranilic acid (II). This step is analogous to the formation of acetanilide from aniline and acetamide. Mayer and Wagner⁴ isolated a small amount of methyl *N*-acetylanthranilate and observed evolution of ammonia when methyl anthranilate was heated with

1. Niementowski, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1895, **ii**, 51, 564.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, **22**, 531.
3. Bogert and Hand, *ibid.*, 1906, **28**, 99.
4. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1943, **8**, 239.
5. Sherrill *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1299.

acetamide. We regard this step as a nucleophilic attack of the nitrogen atom of (I) on the carbonyl carbon atom of the amide, thus:

This attack will be inhibited, when (R) is alkyl or aryl, partly due to the steric effect and partly due to the decreased electrophilic character of the carbonyl carbon, following delocalisation. This mechanism will be in conformity with the observed fact that the yield of 4-ketoquinazoline derivative in the Niementowski reaction decreases with the increase in molecular weight of the amide.

The second stage in the proposed course of the reaction^{3,4} comprises the formation of the ammonium salt of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (III) from (II) and ammonia, liberated in the first stage of the reaction, and subsequent dehydration of (III) to *N*-acetylanthranilamide (IV); in the final stage, (IV) undergoes cyclodehydration, leading to the formation of 2-*R*-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline (V). Both the second and the third steps in the proposed course of the reaction are purely inferential as none of the intermediates, (III) and (IV), has been isolated by these authors⁴. The inference is drawn from the fact that conversion of (III) and of (IV) to (V) are well-known, independent 4-ketoquinazoline syntheses⁶⁻⁷.

Failure in the isolation of the intermediate (IV) may be due to the commonly observed, extremely facile cyclodehydration of (IV) to (V). Zentmeyer and Wagner⁷ reported that the cyclodehydration of *N*-*o*-substituted arylanthranilamide was inhibited greatly by presence of the *ortho*-substituent. This suggests that if the formation of (IV) is one of the intermediate steps involved in this synthesis, it may be possible to isolate the *N*-*o*-chlorophenylanthranilamide (IVa) on condensation of *N*-*o*-chlorophenylanthranilic acid (IIa) with formamide. This has been actually realised in practice. When (IIa) was heated with a slight excess of formamide at 160° for 3 hr., *N*-*o*-chlorobenzoylanthranilamide (IVa) was isolated. For the sake of comparison, (IVa) has been synthesised by condensing 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-3, 1, 4-benzoxazone with ammonia. Compound (IVa) on treatment with a hot dilute alkali solution afforded 2-*o*-chlorophenyl-4-ketoquinazoline (Va). As has been reported⁷, (IVa) could not be cyclodehydrated to (Va) on heating it at 250° in presence of zinc chloride.

The mode of formation of *N*-acetylanthranilamide (IV) through the ammonium salt of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (III), as suggested originally by Bogert and Gotthelf², is far from

6. Bogert and Steiner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 1327.

7. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **14**, 969.

8. Smith and Stephen, *Tetrahedron*, 1957, **10**, 39.

9. Murr and Bogert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 729.

10. Wadge and Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4420.

convincing. Under the conditions of the reaction, most of the ammonia liberated in the first stage would escape before it can react with (II) to form (III); further, the dehydration of the ammonium salt (III) to the amide (IV) would require a much higher reaction temperature than that prevailing in the actual synthesis. In fact, it is most likely that the conversion of the *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (II) to the amide (IV) is a transamidoylation reaction as formulated below. Such a possibility is indicated by the fact that evolution of formic acid is detected during the condensation of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (IIa) with formamide and that of acetic acid is detected when (IIa) is condensed with acetamide at 180°; in both these reactions the same product, viz., 2-methyl-4-ketoquinazoline, is formed. The cyclodehydration of (IV) to the 2-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline may be regarded as a nucleophilic attack of N-3 nitrogen atom on the carbonyl carbon atom C-2 acting as an electrophile, as formulated below :

The present work has thus provided a direct evidence for the course of the Niementowski synthesis and a modification for the same reaction which has increased its applicability. Further work regarding adapting this modified method for the synthesis of Bz-substituted 4-ketoquinazoline derivatives is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Acetylanthranilic acids used here were synthesised by the methods described in literature.

General Procedure for the Modified Niementowski 4-Ketoquinazoline Synthesis.—The *N*-acetylanthranilic acid (0.1*M*) was heated with formamide (0.15*M*) at the specified

temperature for 3 hr. and cooled. The solid product was broken up, treated with a bicarbonate solution, and then crystallised from ethanol. From the bicarbonate extract, the unchanged *N*-acetylthranilic acid was recovered on acidification. The details regarding the characteristics of 2-substituted-4-ketoquinazolines and the reaction temperatures are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
2-(R)-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline.

R.	Obtained from.	Reaction temp.	% Yield	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen Found.	% Nitrogen Req'd.	Ref. No.
Me*	<i>N</i> -Acetyl-A†	150°	83	238-39°	C ₉ H ₉ ON ₂	17.2	17.5	7
Et	<i>N</i> -Propionyl-A	160°	60	235°	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₂	15.9	16.1	7
Pr	<i>N</i> -Butyryl-A	160°	60	206-207°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂	14.6	14.8	7
Pb	<i>N</i> -Benzoyl-A	165°	65	236°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₂	12.7	12.6	8
CH ₃ , Ph	<i>N</i> -Phenylacetyl-A	160°	79	254°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ON ₂	11.5	11.9	10
(CH ₂) ₂ .Ph	<i>N</i> -β-Phenylpropionyl-A	100°	75	210-11°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ON ₂	11.1	11.2	9
CH=CH.Pb	<i>N</i> -Cinnamoyl-A	150°	**	249°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₂	11.7	11.3	8
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ .Ph	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoyl-A	180°	73	352°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₃	15.4	15.7	8,7
<i>p</i> -OMe	<i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Anisoyl-A	180°	68	245-46°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	10.9	11.1	8

N.B. The sticky product repeatedly stirred with acetone and so yield is not reported.

*2-Methyl-4-ketoquinazoline was also formed on heating *N*-acetylthranilic acid (0.1*M*) with acetamide (0.15 *M*) at 180° for 3 hr.

**This was obtained as a sticky solid. It was repeatedly stirred in acetone and crystallised from EtOH. Hence yield has not been reported.

†A stands for anthranilic acid.

Condensation of N-o-Chlorobenzoylanthranilic Acid with Formamide: Formation of N-o-Chlorobenzoylanthranilic Acid (IVa).—This condensation, when effected following the conditions described in the general procedure at 160°, furnished a white sticky solid. It was dried, powdered, stirred in acetone-petroleum mixture (1:4), and filtered. It was finally crystallised twice from ethanol as a white powder, m.p. 200-202°. It did not depress on admixture the m.p. of the same product prepared by an alternative method (*vide infra*). (Found: N, 10.0. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₁O₂N₂Cl: N, 10.2%).

2-o-Chlorophenyl-4-ketoquinazoline (Va) was formed on heating (IVa) (0.5 g.) with a 10% NaOH solution (5 ml) on a water bath for ½ hr., followed by acidification of the filtered reaction mixture with dilute acetic acid. It was crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: N, 10.8. C₁₄H₉ON₂Cl requires N, 10.9%).

2-o-Chlorophenyl-3,1,4-benzoxazone.—A mixture of *N*-o-chlorobenzoylanthranilic acid (IIa) (1.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) was refluxed at 140° for 15 min. The crystalline solid separating from the cooled reaction mixture was filtered and washed free of acetic anhydride with minimum amount of dry light petroleum. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum (1:4) in white needles, m.p. 139-40° (lit.⁷ m.p. 139-40°). (Found: N, 5.3. Calc. for C₁₄H₈O₂NCl: N, 5.4%).

Reaction of 2-o-Chlorophenyl-3,1,4-benzoxazone with Ammonia: Formation of (IVa).—To the preceding benzoxazone (1 g.), dissolved in ethanol (10 ml), ammonium

NIEMENTOWSKI 4-KETOQUINAZOLINE SYNTHESIS

carbonate (1 g.) and liquor ammonia (5 ml) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. and then diluted with water (50 ml). The solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol as a white powder, m.p. 200-202° (lit.⁷ m.p. 199-200°). (Found: N, 10.0. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_2Cl$: N, 10.2%).

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. R. D. Patel, Head of the Post-graduate Department of Chemistry, for providing facilities, to Dr. B. N. Mankad for taking interest in the work, and to the C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for awarding a junior research fellowship to V. S. P.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
VALLABHBHAI VIDYAPRETH,
VALLABH VIDYARAGAR.

Received February 18, 1965.